

Cultural Perspectives in Manju Kapur's *A Married Woman*

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India in the twenty-first century is not only known for the outstanding achievement in the field of science and technology or gradually attaining materialistic prosperity, but also for remarkable achievement of the writers in the literary world. There are a large number of writers who have shown their unique talent in delineating the hopes and aspirations and failures and frustrations of the individuals in their literary works, especially in novels. Indian novelists have got recognition and world-wide acceptance for their outstanding contribution both in India and in abroad also. They show their supremacy among the Western counterparts in terms of thematic and stylistic perception. It also seems that Indian novelists writing in English have marginalized the other genres of literature like poetry, drama, etc.

Among the novelists, especially the woman novelists have shown stern consistency and stamina to throw light on some of the important issues and trends. The woman novelists like Shobha De, Kiran Desai, JhumpaLahiri, ManjuKapur, etc., have shown unique perception in terms of raising slogan for the improvement in the condition of women in the male-dominated society. They try to present some of the esoteric facts concerning to internal problem faced by women in the fast-developing Indian society in the twenty-first century. All these novelists try to discover women within women and their place in the new space in the typical traditional Indian society which is still in dilemma to provide desired place to them.

ManjuKapur is one of the most authentic and remarkable as far as traditional story-telling is concerned. In all her five novels, she has narrated the real life of Indians, especially Indian women in different contexts and milieu. In her novels like *Difficult Daughters*, *A Married Women*, *Home*, *The Immigrant* and *Custody* are quite unique in searching new space for women belonging to middle-class or upper-middle class. In her novels, she tries to highlight the new consequences of husband-wife relationship and man-woman relationship. Her feminist stance is quite clear in the characterization. *Virmati*, *Astha*, *Nisha*, *Nina* and *Shagun* are some of the memorable woman characters in her novels who represent different modern perceptions, plea for liberty and continuous search of the place

of women in the male dominated society. All these characters seem real and live because they realistically present the facets of modern life and its different consequences.

Manju Kapur's women are portrayed within the periphery of their respective territories subject to gender prejudice and oppressed to the level of giving up individual identity. In all her novels ManjuKapur place emphasis on the cultural conditioning of the girl child in an Indian setup. While most novels dealing with feminist issues begin with the problems affecting the marital life of an urban educated woman, the novels of ManjuKapur trace the painful voyage of the heroines from childhood into adulthood.

Kapur's women are divided into two categories: the elderly women who are carriers of culture, and the younger women who defy the culture. The older women are submissive and their lives are dominated by men. Younger women are educated and bold. They fight for their right to be individuals. Her protagonists struggle for self-reliance. The struggle begins from home. It comes out as mother versus daughter dichotomy. The nature of this struggle is complex as the women have to fight on diverse levels such as physical, emotional, familial, social, economic etc.

Among Kapur's five novels, *A Married Woman* seems to be revolutionary in initiating different kind of home morality associated with feminism. The novel deals with the life of Astha, her marriage with Hemant, her association with Pip and her involvement in social and political activities. Astha's journey in this novel can be analysed in the light of feminism in the new era of liberty and freedom.

Astha's stories are a different kind of disappointment. She is educated, she is an artist, she has a loving and dutiful husband, she has a good house, she is economically stable, but she aspires for different kind of freedom, which is quite symbolic and also complicated. Her story may not be story of every Indian woman, but at the same time it challenges the traditional and conventional existence of a woman in which Astha locates herself. Her journey clearly symbolizes the transformation in the outlook of the women after independence. The novel can be studied to two ways, firstly in the light of Astha-Hemant relationship has been presented in the manner of middle class circumstance while Astha-Pip relationship.

At the age of sixteen, Astha was attracted towards a boy named Bunty, her neighbour. Many letters were exchanged between them from time to time. She lived in her own world which is full of fantasy. Astha was very curious about her education and she has the realization that only education can bring real freedom in her life. She was admitted in a college for higher education. After her breakage from Bunty, she finds a new love in the arms of Rohan. They begin to start physical interaction. Any kind of relationship between boys and girls before marriage is unaccepted in Indian society. Their relationship are closed to each other on certain terms. Finally, Astha was married to Hemant.

Astha's marriage life with Hemant is very much happy and satisfactory in the beginning. He gives her all the love, security, material comforts that a married woman in Astha's place would have yearned for: "Astha's heart is as full of love as the lake was full of water" (42). He appreciates her talents of writing and painting. Like a typical Indian married woman, she performs and plays the role of daughter-in-law and wife. But soon the dullness and monotony began to occupy her life. In due course, Astha becomes pregnant and gives birth to a girl child, Anuradha. And happiness spreads everywhere in the family.

Then when Astha becomes pregnant for second time, she is able to understand the true colour of her husband. She is shocked when her husband declares, "I want to have my son soon" (61). This situation in the novel clearly picturizes the exact condition of gender discrimination which is rooted in Indian society. Astha's mind is enveloped with fear and worries during her second pregnancy. Hemant doesn't care for her feelings. To her greatest relief, she gives birth to a son, Himanshu.

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Gender discrimination is visible clearly in the novel, when the naming ceremony of their new born baby is held-“The naming ceremony of the boy was carried out on a much grander scale than that of Anuradha’s” (68). As days pass on, Astha finds difficulty in playing dual roles. She is determined not to give up her job and successfully manages both the roles. She feels suffocated with her responsibilities to the growing needs of the family imposed on her. This stressful life has affected her both physically and mentally. She seeks consolation in writing poems and in painting. Astha’s psychological condition is revealed through her sketching and poems also. To communicate her feelings to Hemant, she makes use of her writing. When Hemant criticizes it, she replies that, “Poems are about emotions”(81). Hemant never minds her feelings. Caged in a loveless and attention less married life, Astha leads a miserable life.

Marriage means sacrifice of personal interest, personal emotions of pride and self identity. Gradually, distance takes place between Astha and Hemant. Astha had brought deformities in her life. She felt the horror of distance from Hemant. She aspired for freedom and she was in search of liberty. She was educated, she was creative, she was sensitive and she needed liberty.

A sudden turn occurs in the life of Astha when she meets AijazAkthar Khan. He is a history teacher and the founder of street theatre group. When Aijaz comes to know that Astha writes well, he offers her to write script for his drama. She collects materials from library, and has written a script successfully. When Astha shares her experience of writing scripts for the first time, Hemant underestimates her talents. He harshly condemns her activist and zealous involvements as “Translating history into theatre is hardly work a donkey can do” (109). On the contrary, Aijaz greatly appreciates her script, her paintings and sketches. His appreciation instills a sense of hope in Astha. Thus with the end of the workshop, Astha’s new hope too comes to an end. After the death of Aijaz, Astha emerges as a social activist.

The novel is not only about the journey of Astha’s ‘innocence to experience’ but the novel also deals with Peeplika who seems to be unorthodox in every sense. She was a complete modern girl. She is a woman who cares for her own feelings and desires. She puts the pleasure of human relationship above caste and religion. She married Aijaz in spite of her mother’s wish. She becomes widow in very young age. Peeplika is always sympathetic in her action towards humanity. She forces her to start a new life. On the other hand, Astha had some other notions.

The novel seems to the portrayal of the characters of Astha and Peeplika searching their identity in male dominated society. They are the typical victims of time and space. They seem to be the typical representatives of the age of the transformation in which women cannot be marginalized. ManjuKapur is aware of this fact. Astha’s aspirations are not simple, her search of identity and plea for liberty and independence are not baseless, and her frustration, depression and hostility are not meaningless. Her unorthodox behaviour is not shocking. She along with Peeplika seems to challenge the traditional concept of society in which women have a little role to play but they show that they are different types of women and they have to play a bigger role not only in home but also outside of home.

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